

ADAPTATION DEGREES OF HIGHER AQUATIC VEGETATION TO GLOBAL WARMING CONDITIONS

Shakhla Efendiyeva

Baku State University, Faculty of Biology

Abstract

Higher aquatic plants are essential to aquatic ecosystems, playing a pivotal role in the production of organic matter and oxygen, as well as the stabilization of aquatic and wetland environments. These plants exhibit remarkable adaptive mechanisms, including structural, physiological, and reproductive changes, enabling them to thrive under extreme environmental conditions. The Absheron Peninsula, with its arid climate, fluctuating precipitation, and significant anthropogenic pressures, serves as a critical study area for understanding these adaptations. Key mechanisms include dimorphism, allowing plants to transition between aquatic and terrestrial forms, and specialized gas exchange systems that compensate for reduced sunlight in water. However, anthropogenic activities, particularly eutrophication caused by excessive nutrient input, present significant challenges. This leads to water blooming, oxygen depletion, and biodiversity loss, further destabilizing ecosystems. This study highlights the resilience of higher aquatic vegetation and underscores the urgent need for conservation measures to mitigate eutrophication and maintain ecological balance in aquatic ecosystems.

Keywords: Dimorphism, bioproductivity, eutrophication, aquatic ecosystems, adaptation

Introduction

Aquatic ecosystems play a crucial role in maintaining biodiversity and ensuring the stability of natural processes. Higher aquatic plants, as primary producers, are key to these ecosystems, influencing water quality, nutrient cycling, and the habitat conditions for numerous organisms. Their extensive surface area increases phase interfaces, making them essential in ecological and hydrobiological research.

The Absheron Peninsula, an ecologically sensitive region of Azerbaijan, faces severe climatic and anthropogenic challenges, including fluctuating precipitation, extreme temperatures, and significant anthropogenic waste discharge. This region provides a valuable model for understanding how higher aquatic plants adapt to such adverse conditions and maintain their ecological functions.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted during the summer of 2023 on three lakes of the Absheron Peninsula: Bulbula, Ganlygol, and Khojagasan. These lakes were selected due to their ecological significance and their exposure to various climatic and anthropogenic pressures.

Field Investigations

Water Quality Parameters: Measurements of temperature, salinity, and water depth were taken using standard field instruments.

Vegetation Observations: Morphological traits of aquatic plants were recorded, with special attention to submerged and floating species.

Species Identification

Key species, including *Batrachium rionii*, *Sagittaria sagittifolia*, *Ceratophyllum demersum*, *Nymphaea alba*, *Potamogeton pectinatus*, and others, were identified using standard botanical keys and taxonomic literature.

Chemical Analysis

Biogenic components, such as nitrites, nitrates, ammonium, and phosphates, were measured using

spectrophotometric methods to assess nutrient concentrations and eutrophication levels.

Eutrophication Assessment

Water bloom intensity, the presence of toxic substances, and oxygen depletion were monitored to evaluate the ecological health of the lakes.

Comparative Analysis

Historical data on aquatic vegetation and water quality were reviewed to identify long-term changes and trends in ecosystem dynamics.

Results and Discussion

Adaptation Mechanisms of Higher Aquatic Plants

Higher aquatic plants demonstrate a range of structural, physiological, and reproductive adaptations that enable them to survive and thrive in aquatic environments:

1. Reproductive Strategies

1.1. Sexual reproduction is often suppressed in response to unstable water temperatures and strong winds, leading to a dominance of vegetative propagation. This ensures population stability in extreme conditions.

2. Structural Adaptations

2.1. The reduction or complete absence of woody tissues in vascular bundles is compensated by the development of aerenchyma, which facilitates buoyancy and efficient gas exchange.

2.2. Morphological flexibility allows stems and leaves to withstand strong currents and fluctuating water levels.

3. Dimorphism

3.1. Dimorphic plants such as *Batrachium rionii*, *Sagittaria sagittifolia*, and *Nymphaea alba* can transition between aquatic and terrestrial forms, enabling survival during periods of water body desiccation.

3.2. Submerged leaves often transform into floating leaves, enhancing photosynthetic efficiency and gas exchange.

4. Gas Exchange and Photosynthesis

4.1. In submerged plants, gas exchange occurs through the entire surface of the leaf due to the absence

of stomata. Floating plants, however, have stomata on the upper side of their leaves, optimizing gas exchange.

4.2. Chlorophyll distribution in epidermal cells enhances light absorption, compensating for the reduced sunlight penetration in water.

5. Root Adaptations

5.1. Roots serve different functions based on species: in *Lemna*, they act as stabilizers, while in *Nymphaea*, they store nutrients and anchor the plant to the substrate.

Eutrophication and Its Impacts

Observations from the Absheron Peninsula

The lakes studied (Bulbula, Ganlygol, and Khojagasan) demonstrate significant eutrophication levels due to increasing anthropogenic pressures. Key observations include:

1. **Water Blooming:** Excessive nutrient input, particularly nitrates and phosphates, has led to rapid phytoplankton growth, causing water blooming.

2. **Degradation of Water Quality:** Toxic substances, unpleasant odors, and reduced oxygen levels were recorded during water blooming events.

3. **Hydroflora and Hydrofauna Decline:** The decay of aquatic vegetation and fauna due to oxygen depletion contributes to secondary contamination.

4. **Role of Sediments:** Organic matter that fails to decompose in the water column settles into sediments, where it undergoes bacterial decomposition, further exacerbating eutrophication.

Long-term Impacts

Eutrophication disrupts the natural balance of aquatic ecosystems, leading to:

Reduced biodiversity due to the loss of sensitive aquatic species.

Altered nutrient cycling, impacting ecosystem productivity and resilience.

Increased vulnerability to climate change due to weakened ecological functions.

Conclusion

Higher aquatic vegetation demonstrates remarkable adaptability to extreme environmental conditions, such as those found on the Absheron Peninsula. Their physiological and morphological traits enable them to maintain ecological stability despite significant climatic and anthropogenic pressures. However, eutrophication poses a severe threat, diminishing their ecological roles and exacerbating water quality issues.

To mitigate these impacts, targeted conservation measures, including reducing nutrient inputs and protecting aquatic habitats, are essential. Sustainable management practices must prioritize maintaining the ecological integrity of water bodies on the Absheron Peninsula.

References

- Andreev, A. N., & Bukharitsin, P. I. (2010). Centennial fluctuations of solar activity and expected climate changes in the North Caspian region. *Geology, Geography and Global Energy*, 1(36), 79–87.
- Bonov, A. D. (1969). Solar data. (2), 93–95.
- Bukharitsin, P. I., & Andreev, A. N. (2006). Rhythms of solar activity and expected extreme cli-

matic events in the North Caspian region for the period 2007–2017. In *Proceedings of the International Scientific Conference on Extreme Hydrological Events in the Aral-Caspian Region* (pp. 137–143). Moscow, Russia.

4. Gnevyshev, M. N. (1966). On the 11-year cycle of solar activity. *UFN*, 90(2).

5. Gurbanov, E., & Rzayeva, A. (2022). Evaluation of decorative properties of some coniferous plants introduced to Absheron Peninsula. *Acta Botanica Caucasica*, 1(2), 3–7.

6. Gurbanov, E., Huseynova, H., Mammadova, Z., & Razaeva, A. (2024). Endemic plants of the Caspian Coast flora (in Azerbaijani territory). *German International Journal of Modern Science*, (91).

7. Gurbanov, E., Ibragimov, S., & Huseynova, K. (2022). Plant ecological research for the bioremediation from pollution by oil and oil products in Absheron Peninsula (Azerbaijan). *Bulletin of Science and Practice*.

8. Gurbanov, E., Huseynova, H. Z., & Ibrahimov, Sh. I. (2020). Methods for determining soil contamination by oil and petroleum products and indicator plants in the north of Caspian Sea. *International Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences*, 4, 84–89.

9. Gurbanov, E. M. (2004). Flora and vegetation of Atropatena province (within Azerbaijan Republic). Autoreferat of dissertation for the degree of Doctor of Biological Sciences. Baku, Azerbaijan.

10. Gurbanov, E. M., & Huseynova, H. Z. (2021). Phytosenological structure of meadow plants spread in the Samur-Shabran plain. In *Behavioral Theories and Practices of Russian Science* (pp. 12–17). Saint Petersburg, Russia.

11. Gurbanov, E. M., & Huseynova, H. Z. (2021). Research and protection of the coastal psammophyte-desert vegetation of Absheron National Park. *Bulletin of Science and Practice*, 7(1), 49–54.

12. Gurbanov, E. M., & Huseynova, H. Z. (2022). New spreading areas of some species in the botanical-geographical regions of the middle part of the Caspian coast. *Acta Botanica Caucasica*, 1(1), 4–8.

13. Gurbanov, E. M., & Huseynova, H. Z. (2023). New distribution areas of some species on Absheron Botanical-Geographical Regions of the Caspian Coast. In *Actual Problems of Contemporary Natural and Economic Sciences* (pp. 13–15). Ganja, Azerbaijan.

14. Gurbanov, E. M., & Huseynova, H. Z. (2023). The rare and endangered plants included in the "Red Book of Azerbaijan" in the flora of the Caspian coast. In *I International Conference* (pp. 265–267). Andijan, Uzbekistan.

15. Hassanpanah, D., Gurbanov, E., Gadimov, A., & Shahriari, R. (2007). Reduction of nitrate accumulation in potato by use of potassium humate for human safety. *Iranian Biomedical Journal*, 11(1), 461.

16. Huseynova, H. Z. (2022). Vegetation of the southern part of the Caspian Coast and its nutritional value. *Biosystems Diversity*, 30(3).

17. Huseynova, H. Z. (2023). New distribution areas of some species of plants on the southern part of the Caspian coast. *Biosystems Diversity*, 31(1), 123–130. <https://doi.org/10.15421/012313>

18. Ismailov, N. M. (2006). *Globalistics and Ecology of Azerbaijan*. Elm.